

LOAD PATH VISUALIZATION FOR FIBER TRAJECTORY OPTIMIZATION OF ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A methodology of fiber trajectory optimization is proposed for Additive Manufacturing of composites. The present method aligns fiber with a physically-determined load path to increase both the stiffness and the strength of composite structures. The fiber trajectories of the open-hole panel and Payload Attach Fitting were determined. It was found that the deformation and the failure index of the optimized fiber trajectory were decreased compared to those obtained by the unidirectional structures. As a result, the strength of PAF was increased by more than four times for the optimized fiber trajectory. The present method also identified the structural members that did not contribute to strength and rigidity, which in turn will enable us to achieve the appropriate weight saving.

1 INTRODUCTION

Additive Manufacturing is an emerging solution that enables the fabrication of complicated three-dimensional geometries without expensive molds and tools. Thermoplastic resins have been used for additive manufacturing; however, their application to structural members was limited due to the poor mechanical properties of resins. Recently, Additive Manufacturing of Composites (AMC) [1–4] has gained increasing attention to improve the performance of the products. In AMC technique, the products are printed by the filament that contains continuous or short fibers. The enhanced stiffness and strength of the filaments have enabled us to fabricate the structural components of space crafts [5], submarines [6], and bicycles [3].

AMC technique provides us not only complicated three-dimensional geometries but also additional freedoms in their design. Especially, the design of fiber trajectory will maximize the potential of AMC technique [7,8]. In the conventional composite structures, the mechanical performance has been designed by a stacking sequence of unidirectional plies [9]. However in AMC, fibers are able to be aligned with the curved trajectory. It is therefore possible that the load in the structures is transferred solely by the longitudinal direction of the fiber, which in turn will be a stiffer structure. Accordingly, a new design methodology is highly demanded to determine the optimized fiber trajectory for AMC.

The curved fiber trajectory has been originally used in the design and optimization of variable stiffness composite panels [10]. Recently, it is also used for AMC technique [7,8]. Yamanaka et al. [7] optimized the in-plane fiber trajectory of the open-hole panel. They used the stream lines of a perfect fluid to describe the fiber trajectories since the stream lines do not intersect each other by their definition. The Genetic Algorithm (GA) was used for the optimization. The Finite Element (FE) analysis showed that the strength of panel was increased significantly. Mitsui et al. [8] proposed the design method of the open-hole panel manufactured by Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) technique. They modeled the curved fiber trajectory by a polynomial function and optimized its coefficients by GA to achieve the maximum strength. It was found that the strength was improved as the maximum allowable curvature increased, which indicated that AMC technique would enhance the structural performance of the panel rather than AFP technique.

While these studies were based on the numerical optimization, few papers have shown that the mechanical performance of the structure was increased by aligning the fiber with a physically-determined load path. Zhang et al. [11] determined the fiber trajectory of the open-hole panel by the principal stress. It was found that the trajectory based on the principal stress improved both the

strength and stiffness of the panel. Unlike the numerical optimization, this method was able to avoid a discontinuity of the fiber orientation between the adjacent elements. However, the principal stress trajectories do not describe the load transfer when shear is dominant [12]. In addition, two trajectories have to be visualized to evaluate the major and minor principal stresses.

Other definitions of load path have been proposed in the past [13–16] although they were not intended to design the fiber trajectory. Kelly et al. [13] proposed a load path based on the equilibrium of the forces which act on the stream tube carrying a constant load. The load paths were calculated by a sequential connection of the vectors derived from stress tensor. This approach overcame the disadvantage of the principal stress trajectories by including shear stress in its formulation. The load paths of the plate with a pin-loaded hole [17] and the yacht structure [13] were described in the reference. Tamijani et al. [14] proposed the load function method to visualize the load path. In this method, the load function was formulated in analogy to the stream function of a fluid, and the structural load flow was obtained as a gradient of the load function. The load function was theoretically calculated when the Airy stress function was determined for a problem. Otherwise, FE analysis was used to determine the stress field. In contrast to the above methods that used stress components, Takahashi et al. [15,16] proposed a definition of load path based on a strain energy. They proposed the index U^* which expresses the connectivity between the loading point and an arbitrary point in the structure. Since the contour of U^* describes the same participation to the load transfer, the load is transferred to the direction perpendicular to the U^* contour. The load path determined by U^* has been widely used in the design of automotive structures [16].

As seen in the reference [11], the physically-determined load path is a promising method to determine the fiber trajectory of the composite structures manufactured by AMC technique. In the present study, a methodology of fiber trajectory optimization is proposed. In this method, the load paths in the structure were visualized by the pointing stress vector [13] and the U^* [15,16]. Since they are the index of strength and stiffness respectively, it is expected that the structural performance would be enhanced by the fiber trajectory along these load paths. In addition, two load paths were combined so that the stiffness and the strength would be improved simultaneously. The proposed method was applied to the open-hole panel under shear loading, and its stiffness and strength were compared with those obtained by a unidirectional fiber orientation. The method was also applied to the three-dimensional structure, *i.e.* Payload Attach Fitting (PAF), and the load paths were analyzed for weight saving.

2 LOAD PATH VISUALIZATION

2.1 Pointing Stress Vector

Kelly et al. [13] defined a load path as the trajectory that transfers a constant load. In this approach, the load paths are defined as curves which surround stream tubes where the force remains constant. Fig. 1(a) shows the schematic of the stream tube. When the force in x direction is constant within the stream tube, the normal and tangential forces along the curves AB and CD make no contribution to the force in x direction. Here, let the normal of such curves be \mathbf{n} , and consider the infinitesimal element having the normal \mathbf{n} as shown in Fig. 1(b). The components of stress at the element are described as a form of stress tensor:

$$[\sigma] = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} & \sigma_{xy} & \sigma_{xz} \\ \sigma_{yx} & \sigma_{yy} & \sigma_{yz} \\ \sigma_{zx} & \sigma_{zy} & \sigma_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where σ_{ij} is the stress component acting on the plane whose normal is in the i direction and pointing j direction. Kelly et al. defined the following “pointing stress vector” using the columns of the stress tensor:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{V}_x &= \sigma_{xx}\mathbf{i} + \sigma_{yx}\mathbf{j} + \sigma_{zx}\mathbf{k} \\
\mathbf{V}_y &= \sigma_{xy}\mathbf{i} + \sigma_{yy}\mathbf{j} + \sigma_{zy}\mathbf{k} \\
\mathbf{V}_z &= \sigma_{xz}\mathbf{i} + \sigma_{yz}\mathbf{j} + \sigma_{zz}\mathbf{k}
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Using the pointing stress vector, the force acting on the infinitesimal element can be described as the vector dot product:

$$\begin{aligned}
F_x &= \int \mathbf{V}_x \cdot \mathbf{n} dA \\
F_y &= \int \mathbf{V}_y \cdot \mathbf{n} dA \\
F_z &= \int \mathbf{V}_z \cdot \mathbf{n} dA
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Since the force in x direction along the curves is zero, it is required that the normal \mathbf{n} is perpendicular to the pointing stress vector \mathbf{V}_x along the curves. Therefore, the load paths are described by the sequential connection of the pointing stress vectors. Three pointing stress vectors (\mathbf{V}_x , \mathbf{V}_y and \mathbf{V}_z) are defined, and they describe the load paths in the corresponding direction.

Figure 1: Schematic of (a) the stream tube having a constant force and (b) the infinitesimal element on the curves [13].

2.2 Load Path U^*

Takahashi et al. [15,16] proposed the index U^* to express the load transfer in structures. The U^* indicates the connectivity between the loading point and an arbitrary point in the structure. This connectivity is called as the “internal stiffness” which represents the rigidity of the connection between any two points in the structure. Fig. 2(a) shows an elastic body with the loading point A and the constraint point B. The point C is an arbitrary point in the structure. For such structure, the U^* is calculated as follows:

$$U^* \equiv 1 - \left(\frac{U'}{U} \right)^{-1} \tag{4}$$

where U is the strain energy of the structure when point C is unconstrained (see Fig. 2(a)) and U' is the strain energy when point C is constrained (see Fig. 2(b)). The strain energy U' has a higher value when the internal stiffness between points A and C is stiffer. The U^* varies from 1 at the loading point to 0 at the constraint point. The value at any point in the structure expresses the participation to the load transfer.

Figure 2: Schematic of the internal stiffness: (a) the original and (b) the constrained structures [15,16].

The load paths are visualized by the concept of the U^* potential. Considering the distribution of U^* value, the contours of such distribution describe the isolines having the same participation to the load transfer. Therefore, the load transfers along the lines perpendicular to the isolines, which is called as the stiffness lines. If the U^* is regarded as a potential, the stiffness lines are obtained by the sequential connection of the following “stiffness decay vector”:

$$\mathbf{k}^{(-)} = -\text{grad}U^* \quad (5)$$

Since the applied load is transferred through the structural members with the highest internal stiffness, the principal load paths are visualized by tracing the stiffness decay vector having the smallest magnitude. It is equivalent to trace the ridge lines of the U^* potential surface.

3 METHODOLOGY OF FIBER TRAJECTORY OPTIMIZATION

In the present study, fibers were aligned with the load paths based on the pointing stress vector and the U^* . Since the pointing stress vector describes a load flow derived by the stress components, it is suitable to visualize the load path around a stress concentration. Accordingly, the strength of the structure will be increased when the fiber is aligned with the pointing stress vector. On the other hand, the U^* is based on the change in the total strain energy. Since it describes the internal stiffness between the loading point and any point in the structure, the stiffness will be increased when the fiber is aligned with this load path. In addition, we combined the above two load paths to increase both the strength and stiffness of the structure. In the present study, the pointing stress vector and the stiffness decay vector were calculated at each element, and they were combined by the weighted average method. The weights were formulated as a function of failure index so that the averaged load path was oriented to the pointing stress vector at the location of high stress and to the stiffness decay vector elsewhere. The methodology of fiber trajectory optimization is described in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Flowchart of fiber trajectory optimization.

4 APPLICATIONS

4.1 Open-Hole Panel

A fiber trajectory of the open-hole panel was determined by the proposed method. Fig. 4 shows the FE model and boundary conditions of the panel. The panel was constrained at the top-left and the bottom-left ends, and was subjected to the nodal tensile force in the diagonal direction. The material properties are shown in Table 1. The material was assumed to be linear orthotropic. Young's modulus and the strength were determined from commercially-available filaments. The initial fiber orientation was set to be unidirectional in x direction. The local coordinate system was identical to the global coordinate system shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: FE model and boundary conditions of the open-hole panel.

Young's modulus [GPa]		Poisson's ratio		Strength [MPa]			
E_x	12.8	ν_{xy}	0.2	F_{xt}	100	F_{xy}	50
E_y	6.1			F_{xc}	-100		
G_{xy}	6.1			F_{yt}	30		
				F_{yc}	-30		

Table 1: Material properties of the filament.

First, the fiber trajectory was solely determined by the U^* . Fig. 5 shows the fiber trajectory and the deformation in y direction. Fig. 5(a) is the result at the initial iteration where the fiber is aligned in x direction, and Fig. 5(b) is the one obtained at 10th iteration. After the optimization, the fiber was aligned to connect the constraint nodes and the loading nodes in the diagonal direction, but the fiber trajectory was forced to avoid the open-hole. A close observation of the fiber trajectory reveals that the principal load paths locate away from the hole. These paths were obtained by the concept of U^* ; loads were transferred by stiffer members in the structure, not by the vicinity of a hole [15]. As a result, the deformation at the loading point was decreased by 4% (from -2.6×10^{-3} mm to -2.5×10^{-3} mm).

Figure 5: Fiber trajectory and deformation of the open-hole panel; (a) at the initial condition and (b) after 10 iterations.

Next, the fiber trajectory was determined by the pointing stress vector. Fig. 6 shows the fiber trajectory and the distribution of Tsai-Wu's failure index. The significant difference was observed between the fiber trajectories calculated by two methods. Unlike the stiffness decay vector, the pointing stress vector aligned with the edge of the hole. This result was obtained by the definition of the pointing stress vector, where the vector pointed to the direction of large stress components (see V_x in Eq. (2)). In this case, the panel was subjected to the diagonal load, and the load was transferred both by the normal stress (σ_x) and by the shear stress (τ_{xy}). Accordingly, the principal load paths oriented in 45° direction at the edge of the hole, which was similar to the direction of the principal stress. Tsai-Wu's failure index was compared between the initial and last iterations. Since the constraint and loading nodes were subjected to the stress concentration, we used the maximum failure index around the hole. As a result, the failure index was decreased by 55% (from 3.3×10^{-3} to 1.5×10^{-3}).

Figure 6: Fiber trajectory and failure index of the open-hole panel; (a) at the initial condition and (b) after 10 iterations.

Finally, the stiffness decay vector and the pointing stress vector were combined by the weighted averaged method to determine the optimized fiber trajectory. Fig. 7 shows the fiber trajectory and the contours of deformation and failure index. The principal load paths oriented in 45° direction at the vicinity of the hole, where the averaged vectors were weighted to the pointing stress vector at the area of high stress. Elsewhere, the load paths located away from the hole to transfer the load by the stiffer structural member. The result showed that the averaged load paths kept the characteristics of those obtained by the pointing stress vector and the U^* . Fig. 8 shows the convergence history of the maximum deformation and the maximum failure index. The results were normalized by their initial values. It was found that the parameters were fully converged after 5 iterations. As a result of fiber trajectory optimization, the deformation and the failure index were decreased by 8% and 55% respectively.

Figure 7: Fiber trajectory, deformation and failure index of the open-hole panel; (a) at the initial condition and (b) after 20 iterations.

Figure 8: Convergence histories of the deformation and the failure index during the fiber trajectory optimization.

4.2 Payload Attach Fitting

As an example of application to three-dimensional structures, the optimized fiber trajectory of PAF was determined. PAF is the structure which connects the rocket structure and satellites. It is mainly subjected to the compressive load from the satellites during the launch and their release.

Fig. 9 shows the FE model and boundary conditions. The structure is constrained at the bottom edge. In the present study, the fiber trajectory was optimized under the compressive load. Young's modulus and strength shown in Table 1 were used. The local coordinate system was defined as shown in Fig. 9, and the pointing stress vector of \mathbf{V}_x was used for the optimization. Assuming that PAF was manufactured by a commercially-available 3D printer, the initial fiber orientation was defined along y direction of the local coordinate system.

Figure 9: FE model and boundary conditions of PAF.

Fig. 10(a) shows the fiber trajectory and the distribution of failure index at the initial condition. The maximum failure index was observed at the intersection of panels. Since the fiber was horizontally aligned, this location was subjected to the compressive transverse stress. Considering

relatively low strength in transverse direction compared to the one in longitudinal direction, the fiber should be aligned with x direction of the local coordinate system.

Fig. 10(b) shows the results after 5 iterations. The principal load paths originated from the constraint nodes and they oriented to the loading nodes. The curved trajectories were observed at the middle of the panel so that the paths were converged to the loading nodes. The failure index was decreased from 4.2×10^{-5} to 1.0×10^{-5} , where the strength of PAF was increased by more than four times.

On the other hand, the reduction of deformation was only 6% and was not significant. Generally, the principal load paths are connected to the constraint and loading points. As shown in Fig. 10(b), the directions of vectors are not consistent within a region surrounded by the principal load paths, where the load is not transferred efficiently. It is therefore inferred that such regions do not contribute to stiffness or strength of the structure and they can be removed without any effect on the principal load paths. Accordingly, the present method will also enable us to achieve the weight saving without any effect on the structural performance.

Figure 10: Fiber trajectory and failure index of PAF; (a) at the initial condition and (b) after 5 iterations.

5 CONCLUSIONS

- The methodology of fiber trajectory optimization was proposed for the composite structures manufactured by AMC technique.
- The present method aligned the fiber with the physically-determined load paths using the pointing stress vector and the stiffness decay vector of the index U^* . Two load paths were combined by the weighted average method so that both the stiffness and strength would be improved.

- The fiber trajectories of the open-hole panel and PAF were determined. It was found that the deformation and the failure index of the optimized fiber trajectory were decreased compared to those obtained by the unidirectional structures.
- The present method also identified the structural members that did not contribute to strength and rigidity, which in turn will enable us to achieve the appropriate weight saving.

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